

Project information

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Tasks in WP2

Task 2.1: Establish the structure for the information platform (INSTRUCT-ERIC, FORS, EMBL, ESF), M1-M6

Task 2.2: Implementation of the information platform (INSTRUCT-ERIC, FORS, ESF), M3-M30

Task 2.3: Collaborative links between eRImote and EOSC development (INSTRUCT-ERIC, EMBL, ESF, FORS, INFRAFRONTIER), M12-M24

Background

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) is a key component in the effort of making the European Research Area (ERA) competitive. The European Commission in alignment with their policy priorities of Open Innovation, Open Science and Open to the World has supported the development of the EOSC towards its goal of ensuring findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR) data. The eRImote project aims to provide solutions to provision of remote and digital access to increase the resilience of the European RI landscape, highlighting the

importance of open science in accelerating innovation. The eRImote consortium brings together [12 partners](#) from the environmental, life, physical and social sciences domains. This cross-domain membership enables the project to identify strategies and solutions for more remote and digital access to Research Infrastructure (RI) services across ESFRI domains. In this context the consortium is well positioned to analyse the work carried out so far in the context of EOSC projects and task forces to facilitate remote or virtual access to infrastructures and provide recommendation for future activities.

eRImote and EOSC Taskforce

To understand the relationship between EOSC, the EOSC task forces and various EOSC projects and remote access provision, WP2 gathered the input from the consortium participating RIs, their data services/EOSC experts and specifically their representatives in the different EOSC Taskforces. The aim of the collaboration was to uncover which activities and outcomes of EOSC projects, task forces, and other EOSC activities, and the planned federated EOSC could contribute to advancing remote and digital access provision. Membership arose from staff that is or has worked on EOSC projects, EOSC task forces, in related eRImote tasks, or both, and included members from all domains represented in eRImote. This provided the opportunity for discussion between different stakeholders and partners, and the consolidation of critical findings in EOSC that are relevant to remote access, and produce key recommendations for how EOSC can advance remote and digital access to RI services.

Membership

Possible participants for the workforce from those research infrastructures in eRImote that are members of the EOSC Association and EOSC taskforces were contacted in order to provide their expertise. The taskforces and their respective contacts are shown in the Table 1.

Table 1. EOSC Taskforce Contacts.

	Euro-BioImaging	Instruct-ERIC	CESSDA
FAIR Metrics and Data Quality Task Force			Mari Kleemola
Researcher Engagement & Adoption Task Force (REA TF)	Mathur, Aastha	Alen Amaro, Claudia: Bonvin, Alexandre	
Infrastructures for Quality Research Software Task Force		del Cano, Laura	
Technical Interoperability of Data and Services Task Force	Heriche, Jean-Karim	Sánchez, Irene	

Long-Term Data Preservation Task Force		Novacek, Jiri	Herve L ´Hours
Financial Sustainability Task Force		Haley, Natalie	

Each of these were invited to the meeting to offer their experiences from their respective taskforces. In addition to these, several specified individuals were invited to provide alternative views and experiences, as well as offer a perspective from the eRImote side. These included Darren Bell who had worked on the eRImote Expert Group on Data Access and security, and Michael Raess who leads the preparation of the eRImote Green Paper – both gave presentations of their findings of how EOSC had addressed remote RI access. Omran Alhaddad also presented the eRImote Information Platform which has been populated with all eRImote documents and services. The information platform includes several documents on access to specific data services, but there were no documents that outline the process for open science cloud services, and access to those at the remote level. Additionally, external partners connected to the eRImote partners were invited, based on their experience with specific EOSC-related activities and projects, to provide a template for how EOSC systems can be implemented, and the requirements for them to be established – this could provide a blueprint for discussion on how similar systems could be implemented for remote access.

Table 2. Participants at the eRImote - EOSC meeting.

Names	eRImote Role	Association
Ayoub El Ghadraoui	WP3	Euro-Biolmaging
Darren Bell	WP3	UKDS
Michael Raess	WP4/WP5	INFRAFRONTIER
Susanne Vainio	WP3	Euro-Biolmaging
Alexandre Bonvin	External	Instruct-ERIC
Oguz Ozkan	WP2/WP5	ESF
Jiri Novacek	External	Instruct-ERIC
Valentina Tegas	WP4	EMSO-ERIC
Ivan Rodero	WP4	EMSO ERIC
Johanna Bischof	WP3	Euro-Biolmaging

Omran Alhaddad	WP2/WP5	Instruct-ERIC
John Dolan	WP1/WP5	Instruct-ERIC
Eirini Xemantilotou	External	Instruct-ERIC
Claudia Alen Amaro	WP1	Instruct-ERIC

Key Findings

As a result of the task force activities; specifically following the presentations from Darren Bell, Michael Raess, and Omran Alhaddad, and a fruitful discussion between the rest of the group, several critical findings were uncovered:

- Focus on Frameworks and Guidelines:** Many EOSC projects focus on frameworks, guidelines, and policies rather than providing support for concrete infrastructure and implementation guides. There is a need for real-world implementation projects to deliver tangible infrastructure for specific purposes, and for longer-term sustainability of such efforts beyond the timeframe of individual projects.
- Fragmentation of Access Protocols:** The landscape of EOSC initiatives and standardising access protocols is fragmented, highlighting the need for a top-down approach to ensure that standardised protocols for EOSC resources and access to these exist for the research community and RIs to follow.
- Need for Operational Information:** Outside of RIs, there is a demand for more information on how to operate within EOSC. While efforts have been made to catalogue RIs and their services in a manner that is EOSC compatible and accessible, the EOSC Marketplace lacks a comprehensive representation of available resources and uncertainties about the sustainability of such catalogues and mapping exercises reduces RI community buy-in for the effort required to complete them
- Remote Access Elements:** Certain essential elements, such as real-time data streaming and accessible compute capacity, are currently missing in EOSC services. This gap hampers the effectiveness of remote access to data.
- Interoperability and Standardisation:** Efforts towards metadata exchange and standardisation are underway, but there is a need to find common solutions and ensure interoperability among services and across disciplines.
- Communication Challenges:** Language differences between EOSC developers and researchers pose communication challenges and reduce accessibility of EOSC resources to researchers, preventing greater crossover and collaboration.
- Legal and Ethical Considerations:** The green paper emphasizes the importance of addressing legal and ethical considerations, particularly concerning data access and security in the context of EOSC.

Deliverable and Recommendations

From the findings of the meeting and discussions, a series of recommendations can be established, providing a framework of how EOSC activities can be more closely and effectively implemented to benefit future remote access provision for research infrastructures.

- **Top-down Standardisation:** Implement a top-down approach to standardise access protocols to EOSC services ensuring compliance and interoperability. To achieve standardisation is preferable to use standards already used in the more advanced communities and effective communication of the benefits to get the rest of the community on board.
- **Focus on Implementation Projects:** Prioritise real-world implementation projects that deliver tangible infrastructure, tools and solutions, and address specific research needs.
- **Bridge Communication Gaps:** Foster greater collaboration and communication between EOSC developers and researchers to bridge language barriers and facilitate understanding and accessibility.
- **Address Remote Access Gaps:** Allocate resources towards addressing deficiencies in remote access capabilities, such as real-time data streaming, compute, storage, and transfer, to enhance the effectiveness of EOSC services.
- **Enhance Metadata Standardisation:** Accelerate efforts towards metadata exchange and standardization to improve interoperability among EOSC services.
- **Provide Legal and Ethical Guidance:** Offer clear guidance on legal and ethical considerations related to data access and security within EOSC, ensuring compliance with regulations such as GDPR.
- **Facilitate Collaboration with External Partners:** Strengthen collaboration with external partners to leverage their expertise and establish successful examples for future projects.

Conclusion

The landscape analysis of EOSC reveals both challenges and opportunities for enhancing its effectiveness as a platform for scientific collaboration and data sharing. To facilitate the fulfilment of the EOSC mission of advancing open science the community represented in this report understand that work is needed to address the identified gaps and implementing the recommended strategies. In particular the focus of EOSC activities needs to be changed to increase engagement and practical solutions with the research community. This is crucial for ongoing development, which can be facilitated by research infrastructures. Provision of remote access benefits from such engagement as data management has been identified as a crucial point in remote access delivery.